

Embracing Connection: The Befriending Model for People with Disabilities

(Context: Bangladesh)

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People with disabilities in the Bangladeshi society complain of various forms of discrimination, abuse, neglect and embarrassing experiences. Behind this is a huge lack of awareness. Socially there is also a belief that " **Disability is a curse and is a punishment for sin.**" According to a survey conducted by the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, the rate of disability in Bangladesh is 9% of the total population. Many of these people are currently working in various respectable positions. But in daily life, these disabled people are often subjected to embarrassing behavior in their daily life.

Kazi Rokhsana is visually impaired. In a recent BBC interview with her, she told about her experience:

"One day I told Rickshawala uncle (rickshaw driver) to get down from the rickshaw, "Mama, stand down and I will take the seat." He sat on my hand to help me. I was losing my balance. I couldn't handle it later. Actually, how to help a blind person. Either he did not understand.

About 12 types of disabilities have been identified in humans according to type. These are autism or autism spectrum disorders, physical, mental, visual, speech, intellectual, and hearing disabilities, cerebral palsy, Down syndrome, multidimensional and other disabilities. Question is how to help them?

Get Permission First

Julian Francis, a humanist has worked for a long time on various projects related to the disabled in Bangladesh. Having two such members in his family, he understood their problems very closely. During his stay in Bangladesh, he was surprised by the different attitudes of people towards the disabled. In this regard, he urged to pay attention to a few issues.

"First, try to see the disabled person as a human being instead of focusing on their disability. It is not desirable to see a person sitting in a wheelchair and ask the person next to him to know his condition, talking unnecessarily loudly to someone who is hard of hearing."

It is also necessary to look at whether a person like the Rickshawala is putting someone like Roksana in an embarrassing situation while helping again. Mr. Francis says, if you see someone with a disability and think they need help, you want to know if they want help first.

"Because it could be that he wants to try on his own, doesn't need anyone's help. It could also be that he's too shy to ask for help."

Only guide the person in a wheelchair, crutches or white cane in the direction shown to them if permission is granted. Let him know what your next direction will be. Ask if the speed at which you are pulling the wheelchair or walking is comfortable for him. Usually, driving a wheelchair or keeping pace with someone is a skill. You may not be good at it.

In this case, if you are new to going up and down stairs, ask the person sitting on the chair - he can give you the best solution. Neither high speed nor low speed is favorable for them. **Find out first if someone needs help or not.**

How to treat someone in a wheelchair?

- Do not touch a disabled person's wheelchair without their permission. If he allowed it, he continued.

- Do not move the wheelchair suddenly or pull suddenly on the handle. It may open suddenly. Stop leaning on it or treating it as furniture.
- Instead of standing and talking to someone sitting in a chair, it's better to sit in a chair next to them and make eye contact with them to make conversation easier. If that is not possible then you can speak standing up. Do not lean too far or sit on the ground, unless the person is very close to you.
- Just because the person refuses help once doesn't mean you won't want to know the next time - don't let it happen.

Mr. Francis' son has autism. While going out with him in Dhaka, some people on the street frankly asked him - "*What happened to him, what is the problem*"? In this case, **it is requested that it is unethical to ask about a person's problem by raising his hand like this.** If you want to talk, talk directly to the person in the wheelchair. Want to know how his day went.

Communication with the visually impaired

Make them aware of your presence when meeting the visually impaired or entering the room they are in. Also, when meeting the visually impaired or entering the room they are in, make them aware of your presence. Introduce yourself. If you have someone with you, introduce them too. Also let them know when leaving after work. Never leave the door half open when leaving or entering the room, either close it fully or leave it fully open.

If you already know the person, it helps to call them by name and introduce yourself. Remember when, where and how you met. **It's a bit difficult for them to recognize you and respond by just saying hello or salam.** Don't ever think that someone with a visual impairment will feel

uncomfortable saying things like ``see you later'', ``see what's up'', ``nice to meet you''. **They take the words very naturally**

However, there is one important thing to keep in mind when it comes to helping the visually impaired. That is: "**Don't touch them suddenly.**" They also want to know if they need any help. Then wait, he will hold your hand if needed. Your 'sudden touch' may startle him or her.

It is more convenient for him to hold you than for you to hold him. Let him hold your arm Don't grab someone while trying to help. This can cause them to be embarrassed, lose balance of movement. Warn them in advance if there are potholes, stairs or steep inclines ahead. Say to step down or step up. There is a small hole in front. It will help them to understand.

Communication with the hearing impaired

It is not the case that hearing impaired people have to speak excessively or loudly. When talking to hearing impaired people, try to face them without touching them first. **It is not the case that you have to speak excessively or loudly to them because they cannot hear you.** If you explain slowly, he will understand.

- If communication with them is to be through his companion, helper or interpreter, then eye contact should be made with both. If you don't understand something, tell him clearly. **Just because he can't hear doesn't mean he can't speak.** If you don't understand, ask to repeat. If you don't understand it, there is no need to pretend to understand it.

- Hearing impaired people are naturally not comfortable going in the dark. Make sure that there is light on your face so that he can see the movement of your lips. If you move your face and eyes excessively while talking, if there is a hand or any other obstacle in front of

your face or if you are against the light, then it will be difficult for the person to understand your speech by moving your lips.

- Tell a hearing impaired person if you do not understand them or if their hearing aid makes a noise. He has no way of understanding on his own if the machine is not working and making noise.
- Let the hearing impaired listen to music. They understand the pronunciation of words from the movement of words and they enjoy this movement of words

Communication with the mentally retarded

Similarly, experts recommend treating children with mental retardation or autism, Down syndrome like ten other children. Many times such children show stubbornness, misbehave. **In all cases, teach him the same way you would teach ten other children.**

There are many who keep children away from physically or mentally challenged people. Many do not allow their children to play with children with disabilities. They have nothing to fear in this regard. These people and their families suffer terribly in such behavior.

Don't neglect people with disabilities, and show no mercy to their families. Remember, like any other parent, their child is precious to them. There is nothing to be afraid of them. These are not contagious diseases. Moreover, if you have a disabled member in your family, then it is very important to involve him in various activities inside and outside the house, it makes them feel good, in a very important way! They may feel unnecessary or insignificant if you do all the work for them.

For those who have a learning disability or learning disability, this does not mean that the person will forget about you. Despite the learning disabilities of many, his memory and sense of humor are excellent. So think when you talk to them.

Try to listen carefully to what a mentally challenged person has to say. There is no reason to think that he has no opinions or thoughts of his own. The most important thing in communicating with them is to be patient. Wait for their reply. give time Do not lose patience

Besides, let disabled people speak with their mouths or gestures, suggests Mr. Francis's. ***"It is not proper to speak for them in their presence, or to speak of them, unless you are their interpreter."*** If someone has a prosthetic hand or arm, greet or say hello instead of shaking hands. If they raise their hands. Don't be shy and raise your hand.

Besides, experts have advised to be moderate in the use of language. It is derogatory to use words such as crippled, lame, blind, dumb, disabled, dwarf, crippled, stuttering, mad, crazy, mad, etc. about a person who cannot walk. Experts have given great importance to another point, that one should not advise anyone unnecessarily and unnecessarily. You can give your opinion if it is necessary for professional reasons but remember, nobody likes unsolicited advice.

In Bangladesh, in some cases, disabled people have to face various taunts. It is very important to know what is the right behavior to know them properly. In a world that strives for inclusivity and understanding, the befriending model stands as a testament to the transformative power of connection and compassion. By actively listening, cultivating empathy, respecting autonomy, fostering inclusivity, and educating ourselves, we can create an environment that celebrates the diverse experiences and nurtures the mental well-being of individuals with disabilities. Through genuine friendships, we can break down the barriers that hinder their sense of belonging and pave

the way for a more inclusive and compassionate society. Let us embrace the melody of the befriending model and weave a tapestry of connection that uplifts and empowers us all.

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